

Socio-Economic Status Of Female Brick Kiln Workers In Yerala River Basin

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Abstract:

This paper focuses on female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin and studies their socio-economic status. Uday Pareekh methodology was adopted to study the socio-economic condition of these female brick kiln workers. This study examines factors such as caste, occupation, education, social participation, land, farm power, material possession and family type. There are total of 146 female brick kiln workers, with the majority belonging to the Scheduled Caste (SC). Their occupation is primarily as labourers, although some also engage in farming. Most of the female brick kiln workers are illiterate, and very few have received higher education. The social participation of these female brick kiln workers is very low. They own little land, and some have no land at all. Their houses are built with unbaked bricks. Since these female brick kiln workers come from other states and districts, they do not own any livestock. Almost all of them own a mobile phone. The number of family members is less than five, and they live in joint families. 52 per cent of the female brick kiln workers belong to the lower middle class.

Keyword: Yerala River Basin, Socio-Economic Status, Brick Kiln, Female Brick Kiln Worker, Uday Pareekh Scale Etc.

Introduction:

Brick kilns are an unorganized and labour-intensive industry. Modern urbanization and demand for bricks for houses have become a great employment-generating industry for skilled and unskilled workers. A region of Western Maharashtra with advanced agriculture. The region has a thriving economy and has long dominated economic activity. India's western industrial belt is witnessing massive growth in the construction sector, which has boosted the brick industry as a complementary industry to agriculture. Farmers in this region have recently shifted their investment to brick production. Hence, the sector plays an important role in job opportunities. People are engaged in this industry throughout the year in a variety of tasks, from tillage to distribution. Workers play an important role in establishing this industry, and investors

see the sector as an important ancillary business to the agriculture sector. This is mainly due to the availability of raw materials and the abundance of water. The people who are basically less literate. The brick industry in the study area is operated in a traditional manner without the use of technology. As a result, a large number of people were able to find work in this industry. But these sectors face the problem of inadequately skilled professionals, market advisors, material experts and trained workers.

Socio-economic status is a cluster of factors including occupation, income and cultural features of the household. The socio-economic status of an individual or a worker can be determined with the help of various factors. It can be measured with the help of factors like income, education, occupation, family influence, material possessions, social status, social participation,

caste, political influence etc. Socio-economic status (SES) is one of the prime factors influencing the health status of a nation. It is the measure of the social standing of the individual or a family and has a wide impact on an individual/family's health, educational attainment, diet, lifestyle, etc.

Socio-economic status is one of the important social factors. Socio-economic status needs to be studied in planning for developmental programs and research in the fields of agricultural extension, community development, psychology, sociology, education, etc. Researchers have shown socio-economic status to be related to values, attitudes, child-rearing practices, school achievement, emotional stability, aggressiveness and dominance, verbal behaviour and many other phenomena.

Objectives:

1. To study of Geographical setting of the Yerala river basin.

2. To assess the socio-economic status of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin.

Study Area:

The Yerala Basin is located in the western portion of Maharashtra State and has latitude and longitude boundaries of $16^{\circ} 55'$ to $17^{\circ} 28'$ N and $74^{\circ} 20'$ to $74^{\circ} 40'$ E, covering a total area of 3029 sq. km. The average height is 592 meters above mean sea level. The Yerala basin has a total population of 918583 as per the 2011 Census. There are 456097 females and 462486 males, respectively, in the population. Regional development is facilitated by the transportation network. The basin has a dependable transportation system. Although the national highway and rail transportation networks are absent, the basin has good road infrastructure. The people are connected by the state highway, main district road, district road, and village route. State highways in the basin are 640 km long, and the basin's overall road network is 6131.2 km long.

Fig. No.1 Location of study area

Data Sources & Methodology:

The main objective is to study the socio-economic status of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin. 146 female brick kiln

workers have been surveyed using the socio-economic status scale developed by Uday Pareekh using a random sampling technique. The socio-economic status of an individual is assessed

with the help of components such as caste, occupation, education, land, social participation, house, farm power, material possession and family type. After filling in the information and

scoring the individual items, the total score is summed up and interpreted in terms of the class as per the **Udai Pareekh revised Scale (Table 1)**

Udai Pareekh Revised Scale			
Components	Score	Components	Score
Caste		Social Partition	
Schedule caste	1	None	0
Lower caste	2	Member of one organization	1
Artisan caste	3	Member more the one organization	2
Agriculture caste	4	Office holder in such an organization	3
Prestige caste	5	Wide public leader	4
Dominant caste	6		
Occupation		House	
None	0	No house	0
Labourers	1	Hut	1
Caste occupation	2	Kuccha house	2
Business	3	Mixed house	3
Independent profession	4	Pucca house	4
Cultivation	5	Mansion	5
Service	6	Farm power	
Education		No draught	
Illiteracy	0	1-2 draught animal	2
Can read only	1	3-4 draught animal	4
Can read and write	2	5-6 draught animal	6
Primary	3	Material possessions	
Middle	4	Bullock cart	0
High school	5	Cycle	1
Graduate	6	Radio	2
And above	7	Chair	3
Land		Mobile phone	
No land	0	Television	5
<1 acre	1	Refrigerator	6
1-5 acre	2	Family	
5-10 acre	3	<5	1
10-15 acre	4	5>	2
15-20 acre	5		
More than 20 acres	6		

Grade	Category	Score of scale
I	Upper	Above 43
II	Upper middle class	33-42
III	Middle class	24-32
IV	Lower middle class	13-23
V	Lower class	13 Below

Result And Discussion:

The scale developed by Uday Pareekh has been used to determine the socio-economic status of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river

basin. Socio-economic status is determined on the basis of a total of 9 factors, such as caste, occupation, education, social participation, land, houses, farm implements, household items, type

of family and number of members. Accordingly, the information on the above elements in the Yerala river basin is as follows.

1. Caste Structure:

In the Yerala river basin, there are female brick kiln workers from the Scheduled Caste,

Lower Caste, Artisan Caste, Agricultural Caste and Dominant Caste. Out of these, the number of female workers with Schedule Caste is highest (36.73%), and the proportion of workers with lower caste and dominant Caste is 21.92% and 15.75% respectively.

Caste structure of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 2)

Caste	Schedule Caste	Lower Caste	Artisan Caste	Agricultural Caste	Prestige Caste	Dominant Caste
Percentage	39.73	21.92	12.33	10.27	00	15.75

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

2. Occupation Structure:

Information has been obtained about Labour, Caste Occupation, Business, Independent Profession, Cultivation and Service in the Yerala river basin of female brick kiln workers.

According to this, the Yerala river basin has the highest proportion of female brick kiln workers of labour (84.93%), and the proportion of Caste occupation is 6.85%.

Occupation structure of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 3)

Occupation	Labour	Caste Occupation	Business	Independent Profession	Cultivation	Service
Percentage	84.93	6.85	0.00	1.37	6.85	0.00

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

3. Educational Status:

A study was conducted on the educational background of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin. This study revealed that the number of illiterate females was higher (57.53%),

while 13.70%% had received primary education. 8.90% had received a middle education, and 4.79% had completed high school education. Additionally, 0.68% of the females had pursued education up to the graduate level.

Educational status of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 4)

Education	Illiterate	Can read only	Can read and write	Primary	Middle	High school	Graduate
Percentage	57.53	6.16	8.22	13.70	8.90	4.79	0.68

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

4. Social Participation:

A study was conducted on the social participation of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin. The majority (54.11%) of the females were not members of any organization.

and 35.62% of the female brick kiln workers are members of one organization. Also, 6.85% of female brick kiln workers are members of more than one organization.

Social participation of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 5)

Social Participation	Member of one organization	Member of more than one organization	Office holder	Wider public reader	None
Percentage	35.62	6.85	0.00	4.79	54.11

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

5. Land:

A study of the Yerala river basin shows that 34.25% of the female brick kiln workers are landless. The number of female brick kiln workers with less than 1 acre of land is 34.93%.

The number of female brick kilns with land between 1 and 5 acres is 23.97%, and the number of female brick kiln workers with land between 1 and 5 acres of land is 6.85%.

Land of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 6)

Land	No land	Less than 1 acre	1-5 acres	5-10 acres	10-15 acres	15-20 acre
Percentage	34.25	34.93	23.97	6.85	0.00	0.00

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

6. Houses:

In the Yerala river basin, 86.30% of the female brick kiln workers live in Katcha houses, and 6.16% female brick kiln workers live in mixed-type houses. The proportion of female

brick kiln workers living in Mixed houses and huts is 2.05%, and some female brick kiln workers did not have their own homes and were living in the houses of other workers.

Houses of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 7)

Houses	No home	Hut	Katcha house	Mixed house	Pucca house	Mansion
Percentage	3.42	2.05	86.30	6.16	2.05	0.00

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

7. Farm Power:

A study of the Yerala river basin shows that 86.30% of the female brick kiln workers have no drought animals. The number of female brick

kiln workers with 1 to 2 livestock is 8.22%. farm power. while 3.42% female brick kiln workers 3-4 drought animals.

Farm Power of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 8)

Farm Power	No drought animal	1-2 drought animals	3-4 drought animal	5-6 drought animal
Percentage	86.30	8.22	3.42	2.05

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

8. Material Possession:

In the Yerala river basin, 97.95% of female brick kiln workers have a Mobile phone

and 71.92% of female brick kiln workers have a cycle. Also, 17.12% of female brick kiln workers have T.V.

Material Possession of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 9)

Material Possession	Bullock cart	Cycle	Radio	Chairs	Mobile Phone	TV	Refrigerator
Percentage	3.42	71.92	2.05	13.01	97.95	17.12	8.22

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

9. Family Size:

In the Yerala river basin, 83.56% of the female workers in brick kilns have families with

fewer than 5 members. 16.44% of the females have families with more than 5 members.

Family Size of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin (Table 10)

Family (size)	Joint: Up to 5	Joint: Above 5
Percentage	83.56	16.44

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

Socio-Economic Status Of Female Brick Kiln Workers (Table 11)

Grade	Category	Score of the scale	Percentage
I	Upper	Above 43	0
II	Upper middle class	33-42	02
III	Middle class	24-32	08
IV	Lower middle class	13-23	52
V	Lower class	13 Below	38

Source: Field Survey and Calculated by Author

Fig. No.2 Socio-economic status of female workers

The study was conducted on the basis of the scale of socio-economic status developed by Uday Pareekh. Accordingly, the female brick kiln workers were classified on the basis of socio-economic status. Accordingly, the proportion of lower-middle-class female brick kiln workers is highest (52%). The proportion of lower-class female brick kiln workers is 38%, and the proportion of middle-class female brick kiln workers is 8%. The proportion of Upper-middle-class female brick kiln workers is 2%, and no Upper-class female brick kiln workers are found. (Figure 2)

Conclusion:

This paper studies the socio-economic conditions of female brick kiln workers in the Yerala river basin. The socio-economic status of the female brick kiln workers was studied using Uday Pareekh methodology. Nine factors, including caste, occupation, education, social participation, land, farm power, material possession and family type were studied. There are 146 female brick kiln workers, with the majority belonging to the Scheduled Caste (SC). 15.75% of the female brick kiln workers belong to local castes. 84.93% of the female brick kiln workers are employed as labourers. 57.53% of the female brick kiln workers are illiterate, while

13.70% and 8.90% have received primary and secondary education, respectively. 54.11% of the female brick kiln workers are not members of any social organization, while 35.62% are members of only one organization. 34.25% of the female brick kiln workers do not own any land, while 34.93% own less than one acre. 86.30% of the female brick kiln workers live in houses built with kachha bricks. These houses are located adjacent to the brick kilns. 86.30% of the female brick kiln workers do not own any livestock. Bicycles and mobile phones are common possessions among the female brick kiln workers. 83.56% of the female brick kiln workers families have fewer than five members.

In the lower class, 38% of the female brick kiln workers are in the lower upper middle class, 52% are female brick kiln workers, and in the middle class, there are 8% female brick kiln workers. There are no female brick kiln workers in the upper class. Therefore, it is evident that the majority of female brick kiln workers belong to the lower upper middle class.

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